

Si-N-O FIBER AND Si-Ti-C FIBER OBTAINED FROM POLYCARBOSILANE

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Summary

Flexible Si-N-O fibers and Si-Ti-C fibers were synthesized from a polymer precursor (polycarbosilane) of SiC fibers. The former were prepared by the nitridation of a polycarbosilane and transparent in visible light and the latter were prepared from a polytitanocarborosilane obtained adding titanium tetrabutoxide to a polycarbosilane. Density, tensile strength and Young's modulus of the Si-N-O fibers obtained at 1300°C and of the Si-Ti-C (Ti/Si=0.10) fibers obtained at 1200°C were 2.22 g/cm³, 1.80±0.37 and 139±17 GPa, and 2.30 g/cm³, 0.94±0.18 and 129±28 GPa, respectively. And they were heat-resisting fibers. Both fibers are considered to be promising as reinforcements in composite materials.

Introduction

SiC fibers were first synthesized from a polycarbosilane by S. Yajima (1). The SiC fibers have high tensile strength and high heat resistance. The SiC fibers of diameter about 15 μm are flexible and can be woven into various fabrics. With the SiC fibers, aluminum composite plate (2) and wire (3) and lithium aluminosilicate glass composite (4) are produced. These composites have high strength and especially the latter has high fracture toughness at high temperatures. They are promising candidates for use in high temperature structural materials.

In recent years, making ceramic materials by the pyrolysis of polymer precursors has begun to attract considerable attention (5). Various SiC fibers (6,7), Si-N-C fibers (8) and Si₃N₄ (9) are synthesized from many kinds of preceramic polymers.

Silicon oxynitride (Si-N-O) and silicon titanium carbide (Si-Ti-C) are refractory materials. The respective long flexible fibers are promising as reinforcements in the metal matrix or ceramic matrix composites, similarly to the case of the above inorganic fibers. The whiskers (10) and short fibers (2-3 mm long) (11) of the silicon oxynitride are produced through nitridation of the silicon-silica powder compact and the whiskers of titanium carbide by CVD method (12). However, long flexible silicon oxynitride and silicon titanium carbide fibers are not obtained yet so far as the authors know.

This report describes the preparation and properties of long flexible Si-N-O fibers through nitridation of a polycarbosilane and of long flexible Si-Ti-C fibers from a polytitanocarbosilane obtained by adding titanium tetrabutoxide to a polycarbosilane.

Syntheses of Si-N-O and Si-Ti-C Fibers

The preparations of Si-N-O and Si-Ti-C fibers from polycarbosilanes (PC) are depicted in Fig.1. The procedures are described in detail below.

Figure 1 Inorganic fibers synthesized from polycarbosilane.

Si-N-O Fibers. PC of a number average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n)=1500 was obtained by the method in reference (13); its atomic ratio was $\text{Si}_{1.93}\text{H}_{4.71}$. The PC was melt-spun into PC fibers. The PC fibers were heated in air from room temperature to 165°C for 18 h and held for 1 h at this temperature, and so were cured. In this heat treatment, the weight gain was 5.4 wt%, which is due to the oxidation of the PC fibers. The cured PC fibers were then heated to various temperatures (1000 to 1400°C) in NH_3 gas flow (purity 99.99 %) of 120 ml/min and held for 1 h at the temperatures, so that Si-N-O fibers were obtained.

Si-Ti-C Fibers. The polytitanocarbosilane (PC(Ti)) used as the starting material was prepared as follows. Three different quantities of titanium tetrabutoxide were added to PC (50 g) of \bar{M}_n =860 in xylene (500 ml). The solutions were heated at different temperatures under N_2 gas flow, so that PC(Ti) were obtained. The preparation conditions of PC(Ti) are shown in Table I. PC(Ti)-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15 were melt-spun at 180°C, 175°C and 200°C, respectively. The PC(Ti)-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15 fibers were then kept at room temperatures in air for 1 week, 3 days and 1 day, respectively, and so were cured. The cured PC(Ti)-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15 fibers and the respective polymers were heated to various temperatures (1000 to 1400°C) in Ar gas flow with heating rate of 100°C/h, so that the Si-Ti-C fibers were obtained.

Measurements

Density measurement and tensile test were made of the Si-N-O and of the Si-Ti-C fibers. Densities were measured by the density gradient tube method with $\text{CHBr}_3\text{-CCl}_4$ mixed solution. The fibers were first immersed in CCl_4 .

Table I. Condition of Preparation, Melt Spinning and Curing of PC(Ti)

Polymer	Additive (g)	Reaction Temperature and Time	Melt Spinning Temperature	Curing Time (Room Temperature)
PC(Ti)-0.05*	17.8	190°C, 2h	180°C	1 week
PC(Ti)-0.10	35.6	225°C, 1h	175°C	3 days
PC(Ti)-0.15	53.4	255°C, 1h	200°C	1 day

* The number shows atomic ratio of Ti to Si.

After removal of small bubbles between the fibers under reduced pressure, the fibers were subjected to measurement.

Tensile strength and Young's modulus of the single fiber were measured at room temperature with gauge length 25 mm and crosshead speed 2 mm/min, with Toyo Baldwin Co.'s universal testing machine, Tensilon UTM-II-20. Diameter of the fibers was measured with a micrometer eyepiece in a microscope. Total of 30 fibers was tested.

X-ray (Cu K α) diffraction measurement of the fibers and of the pyrolytic products was made with Rigaku Denki's Rotaflex RU-200 apparatus with a PG monochromator.

The X-ray microanalysis was made of the Si-N-O fibers using EMX-SM of Shimadzu Seisakusho Ltd. An electron acceleration voltage was 10 kV and an absorption current 1×10^{-8} A.

Results and Discussion

Si-N-O Fibers

The cured PC fibers were heated at temperatures from 1000°C to 1400°C in NH₃ gas, so that the inorganic fibers of diameter 13 μ m were obtained. The fibers were colorless and transparent in visible light. They were insulating. The cross section of the fibers was examined by electron probe microanalysis (EPMA). Si, N and O could be observed, but not carbon. The atomic ratio of the fibers obtained at 1400°C was SiN_{1.15}O_{0.47}.

X-ray diffraction patterns of the inorganic fibers obtained at the respective temperatures are shown in Fig. 2. The patterns are all broad, indicating the amorphous state. The inorganic fibers are crystallized gradually by increasing the heat treatment temperature (14).

On the other hand, the PC was heated up to 1400°C in NH₃ gas flow at rate of 120 ml/min. The product was obtained in a 40 wt% yield. Its X-ray diffraction patterns indicated α -Si₃N₄ crystal. The chemical formula was shown to be SiN_{1.24} by chemical analysis. It was indicated that the PC was converted to Si₃N₄ by the heat treatment in NH₃ gas.

The inorganic fibers obtained are shown to be amorphous silicon oxynitride from the results of EPMA, X-ray diffraction patterns of Fig. 2 and by

reference to nitridation of the PC.

Fig. 3 shows density, Young's modulus and tensile strength of the Si-N-O fibers vs. the heat treatment temperature. Density and Young's modulus increase with heat treatment temperature and their values at 1400°C are 2.59 g/cm³ and 188±7 GPa respectively. Tensile strength is 1.80±0.37 GPa at 1300°C and decreases to 1.29±0.32 GPa at 1400°C. Young's moduli of the Si-N-O fibers are similar to those of the SiC fibers (15). Densities of the Si-N-O fibers are lower than those of the SiC fibers below 1300°C. Tensile strength of the Si-N-O fibers is a maximum at 1300°C and decreases at 1400°C, and tensile strength of the SiC fibers is a maximum at 1200-1250°C and decreases above 1300°C. This decrease is due to the crystallization of β-SiC, evolution of CO gas and vaporization of SiO above 1300°C.

Si₂N₂O decomposes to Si₃N₄, SiO (gas) and N₂ (gas) when it is heated above 1500°C (16). In the Si-N-O fibers, the increase of density and Young's modulus and the decrease of tensile strength at 1400°C are considered to be related to this decomposition.

Heat Resistance of Si-N-O Fibers

The Si-N-O fibers obtained at 1400°C were heated at various temperatures (1000 to 1400°C) in Ar gas flow and in air for 1 h, in order to examine the heat resistance of the Si-N-O fibers. The tensile strength and Young's modulus of the heat treated Si-N-O fibers were measured at room temperature. Fig. 4 shows σ_1/σ_0 and E_1/E_0 , that is, the ratio of the tensile strength after and before the heat treatment and Young's modulus, both for Ar gas flow and air.

In the case of Ar gas, the Si-N-O fibers keep their strength in the temperature range of 1000 to 1400°C. Young's modulus increases at 1300°C and 1400°C, possibly due to the crystallization of the fibers. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the Si-N-O fibers heat treated at 1300°C became sharper in comparison with that at 1200°C.

Figure 2 X-ray diffraction patterns of the Si-N-O fibers obtained at 1000 to 1400°C.

Figure 3 Density, Young's modulus and tensile strength of the Si-N-O fibers obtained at 1000 to 1400°C.

In the case of air, the tensile strength drops rapidly at 1300°C. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the Si-N-O fibers heat treated in air at 1200°C indicated amorphous silicon oxynitride, but the patterns at 1300°C indicated α -cristobalite. The strength drop at 1300°C is due to the occurrence of α -cristobalite by the oxidation of the silicon oxynitride.

Pyrolytic Process of PC(Ti) Precursor of Si-Ti-C Fibers.

Number average molecular weights (\bar{M}_n) of PC(Ti) obtained are shown in Table II. \bar{M}_n increases with the quantity of titanium tetrabutoxide added. The TG curve in pyrolytic process of PC(Ti) indicated that the weight residue increased with the quantity of titanium tetrabutoxide added. Fig. 5 shows X-ray diffraction patterns of the PC(Ti) pyrolytic products at 1200°C and 1500°C. The product at 1200°C consists of microcrystalline β -SiC, TiC type compound and α -quartz. At 1500°C, the product consists of β -SiC crystal and TiC type compound. X-ray diffraction peak positions of β -SiC are almost similar to those of TiC. The diffraction peak at $2\theta \sim 35.7$ corresponds to (111) of β -SiC and to (111) of TiC (17). The peak at $2\theta \sim 41.4$ corresponds to (200) of β -SiC and to (200) of TiC. The relative intensity (I/I_1) is 100 for (111) and 20 for (200) in β -SiC. I/I_1 is 80 for (111) and 100 for (200) in TiC. The ratio of the intensity at $2\theta \sim 35.7$ to that at $2\theta \sim 41.4$ decreases with increasing ratio of Ti/Si. TiC in the pyrolytic product thus increases with increasing ratio of Ti/Si in the PC(Ti).

Preparation of Si-Ti-C Fibers

Si-Ti-C (STC) fibers were prepared on the basis of the characterization of PC(Ti) pyrolytic products. STC-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15 fibers were prepared from PC(Ti)-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15, respectively. X-ray diffraction patterns of the STC-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15 fibers obtained at 1200°C and at 1400°C are shown in Fig. 6. The patterns indicate a mixture of β -SiC, TiC and α -cristobalite. The diffraction peak of $2\theta \sim 22.0$ is (101) of α -cristobalite.

Figure 4 Variations in tensile strength (σ_1/σ_0) and Young's modulus (E_1/E_0) of the Si-N-O fibers at higher temperatures.

Table II. \bar{M}_n and Weight Residue (at 1200°C) of PC(Ti)

PC(Ti)	\bar{M}_n	Weight Residue(%)
PC	860	27
PC(Ti)-0.05	1980	46
PC(Ti)-0.10	2170	51
PC(Ti)-0.15	2630	52

α -cristobalite occurs because the PC(Ti) fibers were cured by oxidation or hydrolysis at room temperatures in air. X-ray diffraction patterns of the STC-0.10 fibers obtained at temperatures from 1000 to 1500°C are shown in Fig. 7. The transition from amorphous to crystalline phase appears in increasing the heat treatment temperature. The STC-0.10 fibers obtained at 1300°C are slightly crystallized, as compared with the fibers at 1200°C. At 1500°C, a sharp peak indicating crystalline β -SiC and TiC is then observed.

Density, tensile strength and Young's modulus of the STC-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15 fibers are shown in Fig. 8. Above 1300°C, the tensile strength decreases, possibly due to the cause similar to that in the SiC fibers. This is explained as follows. Above 1300°C, there occur crystallization of β -SiC and TiC, evolution of CO gas and vaporization of SiO, resulting in a drop of the strength; it is almost nil at 1500°C.

Young's modulus of the STC-0.15 fibers are less than those of the STC-0.05 and -0.10 fibers, because the amount of α -cristobalite is large, compared with those in the STC-0.05 and -0.10 fibers, as indicated in Fig. 6.

Figure 5 X-ray diffraction patterns of various PC(Ti) pyrolytic products.

Conclusions

Si-N-O fibers were synthesized by nitridation of polycarbosilane, the precursor of SiC fibers. The Si-N-O fibers were in amorphous state and transparent in visible light. The fibers obtained at 1400°C kept their tensile strength and Young's modulus up to 1200°C in air and up to 1400°C in Ar gas.

Si-Ti-C fibers were synthesized from polytitanocarbosilane obtained using polycarbosilane and titanium tetrabutoxide. Properties of the fibers varied with the quantity of titanium tetrabutoxide added. The density increased and the tensile strength and Young's modulus decreased with the quantity of titanium tetrabutoxide added.

In the future, inorganic fibers with various properties will be required as reinforcements in composite materials, because of the need for composite materials with various properties. Si-N-O fibers and Si-Ti-C fibers obtained in the authors' laboratory are promising as composite material reinforcements.

In addition to SiC fibers, Si-N-O fibers and Si-Ti-C fibers were synthesized from polycarbosilane, and Si₃N₄ fibers may also be prepared from this

polymer. Several different inorganic fibers, promising reinforcements in composite materials, are produced from polycarbosilane, which is highly useful as the starting materials.

Figure 8 Density, Tensile strength and Young's modulus of the STC-0.05 (○), -0.10 (△) and -0.15 (□) fibers.

Figure 6 X-ray diffraction patterns of the STC-0.05, -0.10 and -0.15 fibers.

Figure 7 X-ray diffraction patterns of the STC-0.10 fibers.

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